

CONTRIBUTIONS OF MINDFULNESS TO IMPROVISATIONAL BEHAVIOR AND CONSEQUENCES ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE AND STRESS OF ENTREPRENEURS DURING ECONOMIC DOWNTURN

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of the relationship between Organizational Commitment, Competence, and Work Discipline on the sustainable performance of Hospital X, Y, Z Type C in East Jakarta mediated by Organizational Culture and Work Ethic. The method in this study uses an exploratory approach with structural equation modeling data analysis techniques with Smart PLS software and analyzed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. From the results of the weighting that has been carried out by researchers using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method, with the results for the Sustainable Performance Perspective, the weighted results get the total weighted score 2.6; Organizational Culture Perspective as a result of the weighted results obtained a total weighted score of 4.2; The Work Discipline Process Perspective is weighted to get the total weighted score 3.4; Work Ethic Perspective The results are weighted 3,4 getting a total weighted score of 3.38; and Commitment Perspective The results of the weighting of 2.6 get a total weighted score of 3.38. The novelty in this article is built on the work ethic and organizational culture at the X, Y, Z Type C Hospital, East Jakarta, a research that applies a sustainable performance strategy based on organizational culture at the Type C Hospital in East Jakarta, which has not been found in previous studies.

Keywords:

1. INTRODUCTION

The current era of globalization opens up intense competition in all fields so that a factor is needed that can support the success of an organization to achieve its goals. In achieving organizational goals a quality resource so that it is able to face competition and change (Turmidzi, 2019). The quality of human resources is one of the factors in improving the performance of an organization or agency. The quality of human resources in an organization, can be reviewed based on the culture contained in the organization.

Organization is a pattern of mutually agreed values and beliefs that are found or developed by certain groups (Prajitno, 2012). Organizational culture is very influential in shaping and giving meaning to organizational members to behave and act, which is passed down from one generation to the next as an organizational character. Organizational culture can be said to be the values that guide human resources in carrying out their obligations and also their behavior within the organization (Sarhan, Harb, Shrafat, & Alhusban, 2020).

Performance improvement is largely determined by human resources who have a high commitment and work ethic, competence and good organizational culture, discipline that can improve performance. The achievement of organizational goals determined by the work ethic of the personnel in it. In Suriansyah's research (2015) it is stated that work ethic has a significant influence on employee performance. Employees who have high job performance are productive employees. Then according to several studies that have been conducted, it has been proven that competitiveness has a direct impact on company performance (Brakaj, Vasilika, & Amali, 2015).

The role of the hospital is getting wider because it has a social function as a health service provider, as well as a commercial function as a health service industry. This condition forces hospitals to apply professional business concepts and strategies in all fields. Getting health services is one of the basic rights of the Indonesian population in addition to education services and legal protection. Health is an important issue related to the impact of environmental changes due to current world developments. The development of industry now has a negative impact on the environment in which the community lives. The growing industry also has an impact on health.

The availability of various types of hospitals in Jakarta, namely Type A, B, C, D Hospitals have different problems. This study analyzes the specific problems of Type C Hospitals in East Jakarta. This study was taken at 3 type C hospitals with different management and not one group representing 8 type C hospitals in East Jakarta. The following is related data regarding policies, programs, and activities carried out by Hospital X, Y, Z Type C during 2019 based on economic, efficiency, and effectiveness reviews with reference to performance indicators consisting of input indicators, output indicators (output), and indicator results (outcome).

Table 1: Data on Achievement of Hospital Program Performance X, Y, Z Type C East Jakarta for Fiscal Year 2019

No.	Programs	Target (%)	Result (%)		
			X	Y	Z
1.	Office administration service program	100	89,57	78,90	87,90
2.	Apparatus infrastructure improvement program	100	90,05	82,80	90,57
3.	Program to improve the development of performance and financial performance reporting systems	100	82,70	89,75	84,40
4.	Health service standardization program	100	85,60	79,90	79,90
5.	Procurement program, improvement of hospital infrastructure	100	89,60	80,02	82
6.	Hospital infrastructure maintenance program	100	90,50	80,60	89,90
7.	Health service improvement partnership program	100	79,80	85,90	90,05
Mean		100	86,83	82,55	86,38

Source: Data processed, 2022.

Looking at the results above, Hospital X, Y, Z Type C in 2019 achieved performance results of 86.83% for Hospital X, 82.55 for Hospital Y and 86.38 for Hospital Z from the original target set at 100%. Thus it can be interpreted that Hospital X, Y, Z Type C has implemented the program with the results achieved are still below the target of 100%. To support the vision and mission of Hospital X, Y, Z Type C, it is necessary to increase employee performance. However, the level of employee performance in Hospital X, Y, Z Type C is still not optimal. This statement is supported by a summary of the summary of hospital employee performance data recapitulation. Table 1.2 Data for Sections in Hospital X, Y, Z Type C from 2018-2019 are as follows:

Table 2: Summary of Performance Assessment Data Recapitulation in Hospital X, Y, Z Type C from 2018-2019

No	Performance Appraisal Factor	Mean					
		2018			2019		
		X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
1	K1 = Discipline	75	80	78	77	78	80
2	K2 = Integrity	76	73	80	79	73	78
3	K3 = Initiative	40	70	80	80	79	75
4	K4 = Skill	78	81	79	81	80	78
5	K5 = Team Work	70	70	75	69	78	80
6	K6 = Loyalty	41	44	65	72	50	76
7	K7 = Work safety	71	68	78	81	70	73
8	K8 = Leadership	35	34	77	69	41	49

Source: Data processed 2022.

Hospital leadership in carrying out hospital management has not been maximal in carrying out performance management as it should. This can be seen from the unplanned recruitment of employees. Employee recruitment is still based on multiple interests. After the acceptance of employees there is no clarity of tasks and functions that must be carried out. Employees work based on routines. Employees work without a clear orientation. There is no planning from the agency. Likewise with employees there is no clear career plan.

In table 1.2. Above it can be seen that the employee performance appraisal in 2018 has decreased, which is below the average so that it affects the achievement of employee performance targets at Hospital X, Y, Z Type C. While in 2019 the graph rose slightly above the average where very influential also on the target of achieving employee performance in Hospital X, Y, Z Type C. Another phenomenon is the decline in the work ethic of the Harapan Jayakarta Hospital (RSHJ) employees, which can be seen from their decreased pride in the organization, decreased work motivation, and decreased work discipline, lack of initiative, reluctance to work hard, procrastination on assigned work and reluctance to cooperate with other colleagues at work.

According to observations made by researchers at X, Y, Z type C Hospitals in East Jakarta, attendance is the main factor in employee discipline. Work discipline is a very vital function for the company because employees who have high discipline will increase the output of the employee, so on the contrary if employees are less disciplined and even undisciplined, it will reduce the company's output.

Based on the recapitulation of employee attendance data, it shows that the percentage of attendance in each year has increased, decreased and always did not reach the target. Starting in 2019, the percentage of attendance was 89.04%, in 2020 there was an increase in the percentage of attendance to 90.63% but had not yet reached the target. Employee attendance data shows that the percentage of employee attendance is still below the target of 100% every year. From the description above, the performance management of Hospital X, Y, Z type C in East Jakarta has not been implemented properly, due to several factors, namely Organizational Culture with Work Ethic, Organizational Commitment, Competence and Discipline.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sustainable Performance

According to McClelland as quoted by (Mangkunegara, 2017), there are 5 (five) characteristics of employees who have high performance, namely having high personal responsibility, daring to take risks, having realistic goals, having a comprehensive work plan and striving to realize it, and take advantage of concrete feedback in all work activities he does. Griffin and Moorhead (2014), explain, "Performance behavior is the total set of work-related behaviors that the organization expects the individual to display".

Work Discipline

According to Sutrisno (2017), discipline is a person's willingness and willingness to adhere to and obey the norms of surrounding regulations. On the other hand, according to Rivai (2015), work discipline is a tool that managers use to communicate with employees and achieve behavioral changes, with awareness of all corporate regulations and applicable social norms, various efforts to increase satisfaction.

Organizational Commitment

Employee commitment in the literature, known as employee commitment, has become a topic of discussion in various studies, both in the sector of profit organizations and non-profit organizations, but the studies conducted so far are still dominantly carried out on profit organizations, namely companies. According to Porter in (Sarhan, Harb, Shrafat, & Alhusban, 2020), explain that employee commitment as employee loyalty to the company, which is characterized by a desire to remain in it to identify with the values and goals of the organization, and a willingness to always attach an organizational identity to theirself.

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is defined as the inherent beliefs, assumptions, values and ways of interacting that contribute to the unique social and psychological environment of an

organization. Sutrisno (2017) states that organizational culture is also known as corporate culture, which is a set of values or norms that have been relatively long gone and adopted by employees as behavioral norms used in solving company problems.

Job Competence

The Financial and Development Supervisory Agency in 2018 stated that competence is something that can be measured, observed, predicted, and evaluated which is reflected in a person's work behavior which consists of a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes can also be interpreted as determining factor for someone to show good performance. It can be concluded that competence is basically the knowledge, skills, and abilities possessed by individuals that have been attached to behavior in various circumstances and tasks in their work.

3. METHODS

This research is a quantitative research, using Cluster Random Sampling technique and obtained a sample of 50 respondents. Data analysis using Component or Variance Based Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS).

4. RESULTS

Table 3: Average Variance Extracted

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Commitment	0,600
Job Competence	0,554
Work Discipline	0,505
Organizational culture	0,512
Work Ethic	0,576
Sustainable Performance	0,502

Source: Data Processing Results

The construct value for all variables has a value of more than 0.5. So, there is no convergent validity problem in the model that has been tested.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (Fornell Larcker)

	Organizational Culture	Work Discipline	Work Ethic	Sustainable Performance	Organizational Commitment	Job Competence
Organizational Culture	0,715					
Work Discipline	0,386	0,710				
WO*OC	0,027	0,251				
Work Ethic	0,250	0,279	0,759			
Sustainable Performance	0,594	0,623	0,314	0,709		
Organizational Commitment	0,753	0,216	0,195	0,398	0,774	
Job Competence	0,177	0,253	0,147	0,477	0,103	0,744

Source: Data Processing Results

The square root average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}) value is 1,000. These values are greater than the correlation of each construct compared to the other constructs. Based on the value of the square root average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}) above, the construct in the estimated model has met the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 5: R-Square

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Sustainable Performance (Model 1)	0,688	0,675
Organizational Culture (Model 2)	0,621	0,614

Source: Data Processing Results

The R^2 value of Sustainable Performance (model 1) is 0.688 = 68.8%. This means that in this study Organizational Commitment, Work Competence, Work Discipline, Organizational Culture and Work Ethic were able to explain 68.8% of Sustainable Performance and the remaining 31.2% was explained by other variables not included in this study. And the value of R^2 Organizational Culture (model 2) is 0.621 = 62.1%. That is, that in this study Organizational Commitment, Work Competence and Work Discipline were able to explain 62.1% of Organizational Culture and the remaining 37.9% was explained by other variables not included in this study.

Table 6: Q-Square

Variable	Q-Square
Sustainable Performance (Model 1)	0,318
Organizational Culture (Model 2)	0,304

Source: Data Processing Results

The continuous performance Q^2 value (model 1) is 0.318. Because the result of Q^2 is greater than 0, it means that Sustainable Performance shows that the model has predictive relevance. And the Q^2 value of organizational culture (model 2) is 0.304. Because the result of Q^2 is greater than 0, it means that Organizational Culture shows that the model has predictive relevance.

Table 7: Hypothesis Result

Variabel Y (Model 1)	Original Sample (O)	T Statistic
Organizational Commitment -> Sustainable Performance	0,027	0,228
Job Competence -> Sustainable Performance	0,300	4,256
Work Discipline -> Sustainable Performance	0,301	3,319
Work Ethic -> Sustainable Performance	0,115	1,807
Organizational Culture -> Sustainable Performance	0,368	3,149
EK*BO -> Sustainable Performance	0,239	3,625
Organizational Commitment -> Organizational Culture	0,700	8,672
Job Competence -> Organizational Culture	0,048	0,555
Work Discipline -> Organizational Culture	0,223	2,472
Organizational Commitment -> Organizational Culture -> Sustainable Performance	0,082	1,982
Job Competence -> Organizational Culture -> Sustainable Performance	0,258	3,068
Work Discipline -> Organizational Culture -> Sustainable Performance	0,018	0,508

Source: Data Processing Results

5. DISSCUSSION AND CONCLUSSION

Direct Effect of Organizational Commitment on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good Organizational Commitment so that it leads to good Continuing Performance at the Type C Hospital. Istiarani(2018) in his research states that independence, professionalism, and competence have a positive and significant effect on performance. The higher the level of independence, professionalism, and competence of the auditor directly increases the performance of the auditor. The independence, competence, and professionalism of the auditors are very important in the implementation of the supervisory function.

Direct Effect of Job Competition on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital applies good job competition and healthy competition so that it can lead to good Continuing Performance at the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with the research of Marlapa, Mulyana, Bambang (2020) and Martini (2020) who stated that the Work Competence variable had a direct and significant positive effect on Sustainable Performance.

The Direct Effect of Work Discipline on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good Discipline in work so that it leads to good Continuing Performance at the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with the research of Anggraini, Gimin and Trisnawati (2016) and Iskandar, Faisal Matriadi, Aiyub(2019) which states that the Work Discipline variable has a direct and significant positive effect on Sustainable Performance.

The direct effect of work ethic on sustainable performance

The East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good work ethic that leads to good Continuing Performance at the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with the research of Syafii & Ulinnuha(Syafii & Ulinnuha, 2018) and Sono (2018) which state that the work ethic variable has a direct positive effect on Sustainable Performance.

Direct Influence of Organizational Culture on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital applies a good Organizational Culture in the work environment so that it leads to good Continuous Performance at the Type C Hospital. Thus, the fact that the results of this study have proven that organizational culture has a significant positive impact directly on sustainable performance.

The direct influence of work ethic through organizational culture on sustainable performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good work ethic and is accompanied by implementing a healthy organizational culture so as to lead to good Sustainable Performance at the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with Sono's research (2018) which states that the work ethic variable through organizational culture has a direct and significant positive effect on sustainable performance.

Direct Effect of Organizational Commitment on Organizational Culture

East Jakarta Type C Hospital. This shows that the East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good organizational commitment so that it creates a healthy organizational culture in the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with the research of Jufrizen, Mukmin, Nurmala, Jasin(2021) which states that Organizational Commitment has a significant positive direct effect on Organizational Culture.

Direct Effect of Work Competence on Organizational Culture

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has good Work Competence so that it creates a healthy Organizational Culture in the Type C Hospital well.

The Direct Effect of Work Discipline on Organizational Culture

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has good Work Discipline so that it creates a healthy Organizational Culture in the Type C Hospital well.

Indirect Influence of Organizational Commitment through Organizational Culture on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has a good organizational commitment that creates a healthy organizational culture and leads to good sustainable performance at the Type C Hospital.

Indirect Influence of Work Competence through Organizational Culture on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has good Work Competence so that it creates a healthy organizational culture and leads to good sustainable performance at the Type C Hospital.

Indirect Influence of Work Discipline through Organizational Culture on Sustainable Performance

East Jakarta Type C Hospital has good Work Discipline so that it creates a healthy organizational culture and leads to good sustainable performance at the Type C Hospital. The results of this study are in line with the research of Fitri, Ratnasari, Zulkifli(2020) which states that Work Discipline through Organizational Culture has a significant positive indirect effect on Sustainable Performance.

Discussion of research results with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Priority determination is based on the opinions of experts collected from a questionnaire which is then analyzed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process method. The use of the AHP method has several conditions where the consistency ratio is below 0.1 or 10 percent. This is an effort that the answers or information obtained by experts have clear conclusions. Determination of factors is based on the method used previously, namely PLS, which uses 3 factors namely training, leadership and competence which are considered to play a role in performance. Companies need to realize that these factors must be carried out by actors, as appropriate. The formation of priorities based on factors is associated with actors as implementers or who can influence the formation of strategies for improving the performance of employees. There are five criteria, namely increasing employee professionalism, team collaboration and learning, improving employee quality and quality, organizational relations and the external environment, and strategic leadership.

Discussion of Research Results Calculation of Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Table 8: Ranking Results

	Name	Normalized By Cluster		Limiting	
Kinerja Berkelanjutan	Komitmen Organisasi	0,07436	5	0,037181	10
	Komptensi	0,29658	1	0,148289	1
	Disiplin	0,23771	3	0,118857	3
	Budaya Organisasi	0,24874	2	0,124369	2
	Etos Kerja	0,14261	4	0,071305	4
		1			
Budaya Organisasi	Keagresifan	0,06177	5	0,007682	23
	Kepribadian	0,26252	2	0,032649	12
	Orientasi Tim	0,09725	4	0,012095	18
	Performa	0,15992	3	0,019889	15
	Sadar	0,41854	1	0,052053	7
		1			
Disiplin	Sikap	0,46729	1	0,055541	6
	Tanggung Jawab	0,27718	2	0,032945	11
	Taataturan	0,16009	3	0,019028	16
	Tepat Waktu	0,09543	4	0,011343	19
		1			
Etos Kerja	Menghargai Waktu	0,23849	2	0,017005	17
	Penyesuaian	0,1365	3	0,009733	21
	Tangguh	0,62501	1	0,044566	8
		1			
Komitmen	Identifikasi	0,25828	2	0,009603	22
	Keterlibatan	0,10473	3	0,003894	24
	Loyalitas	0,63699	1	0,023684	14
		1			
Komptensi	Kemampuan	0,28438	2	0,04217	9
	Kepercayaan	0,47286	1	0,07012	5
	Pengetahuan	0,1699	3	0,025194	13
	Skill	0,07286	4	0,010804	20
		1		1	

Source: Data Processing Results

At this stage, each perspective will be calculated and the weight of each perspective will be known. Then in the performance measurement criteria, the scores contained in this calculation

are obtained from interviews with employees. The criteria for measuring employee performance are carried out with references (Rusindiyatno, 2009):

- a. For a score of $\leq 1,8$, it means that the employee's performance is very less.
- b. For a score of $\leq 2,6$ it means less employee performance.
- c. For a score of $\leq 3,4$ it means moderate employee performance.
- d. For a score of $\leq 4,2$ it means good employee performance.
- e. For a score of $\leq 5,0$ it means employee performance is very good.

From the results of the weighting that has been carried out by researchers using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. The calculation of the first and second methods produces a conclusion. As previously stated, that in formulating a plan or strategy must consider rationality, capability, acceptability, feasibility, resulting in the Sustainable Performance Perspective the weighted results get a total weighted score of 2.6 (Organizational Commitment Indicator the lowest weighted result, in this case organizational commitment which is not good affects the decline in continuous performance in the Type C Hospital. The weighted organizational culture perspective results in a total weighted score of 4.2 (the indicator of employee aggressiveness is not good, causing an unhealthy Organizational Culture and affecting the decline in sustainable performance in Type C Hospitals). The Work Discipline Process Perspective as a result of the weighting results in a total weighted score of 3.4 (the timely indicator of the weighting results is moderate, in this case it proves that the Work Discipline factor affects the Sustainable Performance of Hospitals X, Y, Z Type C, East Jakarta) . Work Ethic Perspective The results are weighted 3.4 getting a total weighted score of 3.38 (an indicator of employee adjustment to the work environment from the assessment of the weighting of the average value and in this case Work Ethic is able to improve Sustainable Performance Hospital X, Y, Z Type C East Jakarta Perspective Commitment Results weighting 2.6 gets a total weighted score of 3.38 (an indicator of low employee skills needs to be a concern and means that it can be categorized as having an effect on decreasing employee performance).

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

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